

Insect resistance

Extent of recuperation from attack of *Dicladispa armigera* after insecticidal control in some rice varieties

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Four rice varieties — Anupama, Chatri, Nungi, and Ratna — were moderately to heavily infested with *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) in farmers' fields at Gohalpur, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, in the 1978–79 rainy season. Before treatment, Anupama had 238, Chatri had 110, Nungi had 48, and Ratna had 197 beetles/10 hills. The varieties were sprayed 3 times with quinalphos at 0.04% at 10-day intervals and their recovery from damage was studied. After treatment the beetle population per 10 hills averaged 1.2 on Anupama, 5.1 on

Effect of insecticidal treatments on adult populations of *Dicladispa armigera*, yield characteristics, and yields of rice, Jabalpur, M.P., India.

Factor	Increase (or decrease) (%)			
	Anupama	Chatri	Nungi	Ratna
Number of adults per 10 hills	(97.56)	(91.83)	(95.19)	(97.97)
Percentage damaged leaves	(49.86)	(54.70)	(62.12)	(74.32)
Percentage damaged leaf area	(77.61)	(73.58)	(94.75)	(81.29)
Tiller ht (cm)	9.31	15.00	10.35	12.74
Number of panicles per hill	106.81	94.00	51.11	325.00
Panicle length (cm)	20.87	20.55	15.58	18.35
Number of grains per panicle	27.99	80.38	90.19	84.42
Grain yield	125.	37.38	41.60	594.44

Chatri, 1.0 on Nungi, and 1.0 on Ratna. The parameters used were adult population, percentage of damaged leaves, percentage of damaged leaf area, height of tillers, number of panicles per hill, length of panicles, number of grains per panicle, and grain yield (see table). They were compared on the basis of averages in 10 treated and 10 untreated plots of each variety. Differences between

treated and untreated plots for each parameter were significant.

Yields in treated and untreated plots averaged 1.95 and 0.87 t/ha, respectively, for Anupama, 2.02 and 1.5 t/ha for Chatri, 1.8 and 1.2 t/ha for Nungi, and 5.0 and 0.7 t/ha for Ratna. The differences in recuperation appear to have been caused by differences in pest severity and in varietal resistance. ■

Reaction of rice cultivars to gall midge

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Twenty rice cultivars from the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, Orissa, were screened for their reaction to gall midge under natural field infestation in an endemic area in Sawantwadi, Ratnagiri, Maharashtra, in 1977 and 1978 kharif. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. The seedlings were transplanted at a 20- x 15-cm spacing. Silver shoots were counted at peak pest incidence in both years. The cultivars were graded as resistant (0–5% infestation), moderately resistant (5.1–10%), and susceptible (10.1–22%).

Twelve cultivars were highly resistant; the rest were susceptible. CR94-72-1 was almost immune to gall midge (0% infestation, both years). CR94-721-3,

CR94-1512-1, and CR200-37 showed less than 1% infestation. CR94-721-3 yielded significantly higher (2.2 t/ha) than most other cultivars. ■

Genetics of whitebacked planthopper resistance

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Several rice varieties were identified as resistant or moderately resistant to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) in greenhouse screening tests at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) headquarters, Hyderabad. The nature of inheritance of resistance of five of those varieties was studied in crosses with TN1, a susceptible variety. Results based on F₁, F₂, and F₃ progeny indicate that a single dominant

gene governs the resistance in varieties PTB33, ARC14636, and ARC14766, and that a single recessive gene governs resistance to WBPH in ARC6650 and ARC14394. All five resistant varieties involved in the study were also found resistant to the brown planthopper at Hyderabad. ■

CORRECTIONS:

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Page 10. In Sam L. Page and John Bridge, *Root and soil parasitic nematodes of deepwater rice areas in Bangladesh*, line 10 in column 2 should read "at BRRI." Line 3 in column 3 should read "(which causes the most spectacular damage to deepwater rice)."

Page 11. In P. G. Cox, *Synergy between benomyl and carbofuran in the control of ufra*, "at 2 kg/m²." in line 6 of text in column 2 should read "2 kg/25 m²."